

D3.4

A strategy report defining collaboration of ENVRI in the international context

Work Package	WP3
Lead partner	CNRS
Status	Final
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	28 February 2023
Submission date	20 June 2023

Deliverable abstract

This strategy report defines collaboration of ENVRI in the international context. The strategy focuses on liaisons with users at international levels to ensure visibility of ENVRI, continuity of alignments whenever they are already established, compliance of ENVRI policies with international standards and strategic coordination towards GEO/GEOSS, other international organisations. ENVRI is producing a significant fraction of the in-situ environmental data that serve facing global challenges of our planet and our societies such as climate change, food security, and prevention of natural disasters. The integration of data-intensive sciences is crucial to create the conditions for reaching the scientific knowledge needed to properly advise policymaking with reliable predictions. The production of in-situ data is scattered across disciplinary boundaries and data users must currently discover and extract data dispersed across many different sources and in many different formats. ENVRI-FAIR data workflow towards a single ENVRI-Hub capable to integrate data from diverse data sources in distributed computing platforms is the response from the ENVRI in the European Open Science Cloud Framework. However, it is clear that the ENVRI-Hub initiative must be integrated into a wider landscape as ENVRI must continue serving customers such as the World Meteorological Organization, the European Space Agency, Copernicus, or the Global Earth Observation. This activity in WP3 and the specific deliverable D3.4 therefore serves the purpose of informing the international partners of ENVRI of the ENVRI-Hub initiative and to ensure that the ENVRI data flow is fully compatible with the international programs and initiatives.

DELIVERY SLIP

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DELIVERY LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V 0.1	18 April 2023	First version of the deliverable, delay in submission to integrate latest developments wrt DestinE and EU data spaces.	Paolo Laj, Ariane Dubost
V 0.2	29 May 2023	Second version revised by PL	Paolo Laj
V 1	16 June 2023	Third version revised by PL	Paolo Laj

DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D3.4 - A strategy report defining collaboration of ENVRI in the international context

1 Introduction

ENVironmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) are composed of the main components of the Earth system - Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, and Biodiversity / Terrestrial Ecosystems. ENVRI are key providers of high-quality environmental research data and services in Europe, collected from distributed in-situ observing systems. These environmental RIs have been primarily established to answer to the need of specific research communities but it has soon become evident that understanding the Earth is not possible without interdisciplinary science. The various ENVRI embraced holistic approaches where environmental data and services produced by different research infrastructures are harmonised and easy to use for scientists from any field of environmental research. These scientists, in turn, deliver new insights into the current state of our planet.

Several EU funded cluster projects like ENVRI (2011-2014, FP7), [ENVRIplus](#) (2015-2019, H2020, ca. 15M€), and most recently [ENVRI-FAIR](#) (2019-2023, H2020, ca. 19M€) fostered the structuration of this highly complex and heterogeneous ENVRI community.

ENVRI-FAIR (ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building FAIR services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research) promotes the development of a set of FAIR data services (FAIR, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for each of the RI participating in the project, which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The project strives to develop an open access platform for interdisciplinary environmental research data, called the ENVRI-Hub. The hub will form an interface to the EOSC and will be realised as the services across ENVRI research infrastructures become progressively more integrated.

ENVRI research infrastructures need to be strongly integrated into larger frameworks to reach their full potential. If the natural playground is Europe, other regional and global initiatives are essential to ensure the relevance, visibility, and impact of RIs. This is especially true for environmental infrastructures as the challenges they need to address are most often of a global nature.

In this context, the objective of WP3 is to ensure the implementation of standards, services and policies developed in ENVRI-FAIR are shared with the wider ENVRI community, aligned with policies of its institutional stakeholders, in particular at member-state level, and compliant with the strategy of its relevant user-multipliers in the Environmental domain (international initiatives and programs) and with strategic partnerships and collaborators in EOSC and e-infrastructures.

One of the main outcomes of the ENVRI-FAIR project is the development of the ENVRI-Hub that will provide researchers with the necessary services to practise Open Science using data and services published in the EOSC by a joint catalogue, adhering to FAIR principles. The the ENVRI-Hub will provide research products and services to EOSC to enhance researchers, citizens, and SMEs involvement in Open Science through the ENVRI Catalogue of Services.

In parallel, ENVRI must ensure that they continue responding to their international stakeholders. Many ENVRI are indeed linked to international partnerships with WMO (World Meteorological Organization) programs, with the European Space organizations (ESA), with the Group on Earth Observation (GEO), with Copernicus, with The European meteorology Network (EUMETNET) and others to deliver data or services. It is important that all initiatives involving the data workflow of ENVRI are communicated to the international partners.

The objective of this strategy is to ensure alignment of ENVRI-FAIR data policies with international initiatives in the field of Earth system Observations beyond the scope of the EOSC to serve a wider number of users worldwide. All the project's developments are EOSC compatible and this connection of

ENVRI and EOSC will be addressed in Deliverable D3.6¹. Besides the interoperability with EOSC, it is essential that ENVRI is keeping a strong link with their international stakeholders, and do not put in place standards and operating principles that would not be in line with those used in the global networks.

Indeed, the Copernicus programme, many GEO flagships and initiatives, and disciplinary international activities will gain more direct and homogenous connection to the ENVRI due to establishment of standards, combined ontologies, and interoperability of scientific data services in the domain.

2 ENVRI-FAIR developments

ENVRI-FAIR targets the development and implementation of a technical and policy framework to overcome discipline boundaries within the ENVRI community. Several in-situ domains have been working on open data policy in cooperation with the European Commission (EC). Copernicus as a customer of ENVRI data encouraged the Near Real Time data transfer.

Within the ENVRI-FAIR project, several services developed by ENVRI were consolidated in the [ENVRI-Hub](#), primarily for data provision (e.g. Open and FAIR environmental in-situ data from the four domains of the Earth system). The Hub is continuously developing through new functionalities ([Catalogue of Services](#), [Knowledge Base](#), [Training Gateway](#), [Science Demonstrators](#)) and new projects. Extended services are also offered at RI-level such as *data* (through specific data centres), *access* (e.g. to observational platforms, experimental facilities, scientific samples), *computation* (e.g. data visualization, analytical tools and software), and *support* (e.g. Education and Training). Data and services will remain in the responsibility of generating RIs, ENVRI-Hub acts as an aggregator. The ENVRI-Hub is not a data processing platform. It is meant to enable this by making the services and data searchable and accessible.

ENVRI is committing significant resources to ensure greater harmonization of FAIR policies among them.

Furthermore, ENVRI-FAIR helps advancing FAIRness of the various subdomains by the implementation of technological solutions on RI level to improve access to data and services. The complexity of the task faced by ENVRI-FAIR is to build on a set of RIs in various subdomains. Harmonization is needed even at subdomain level.

For instance, the atmospheric domain aims at having harmonized methodologies and procedures within the RIs for precise high-quality data with rich metadata and known uncertainty. This subdomain also aims at establishing synergies and common solutions when feasible and beneficial to serve users. This work intends to become reference work (for instance vocabulary) with potential to be exported to a higher level with the international framework. The vocabulary work is linked to the Research Data Alliance (RDA) to ensure it is taken up at a higher level.

The solid earth subdomain is more advanced in this harmonization work and is already leaning towards ensuring sustainable and universal use and reuse of multidisciplinary solid Earth science data and products fostering state of the art research and innovation. Those data are close to be interoperable. The challenge now is not only to have multidisciplinary data in the same domain but to look at cross-disciplinarity.

3 ENVRI relations with European/international institutions and networks

International stakeholders have been identified as one of the four key stakeholders groups of the ENVRI community and are prioritized by ENVRI communications when planning joint activities². The challenges addressed by ENVRI are global and interdisciplinary, and answering them requires interoperability across borders and scientific disciplines. That is why it is necessary to engage with

¹ ENVRI-FAIR Deliverable D3.6 “A strategy report defining the connection of ENVRI in EOSC” to be published M52 (April 2023).

² ENVRI-FAIR D2.2 ENVRI Community building, engagement and communications strategy, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6532029>

international players and keep a dialogue with them about the (future) developments. Collaboration with these stakeholders will extend ENVRI's impact globally and ensure uptake of services by the wider user community. It is seen as necessary to raise their interest and further involve them.

During the course of the project, ENVRI engaged with the following stakeholders to embed the ENVRI among the international actors in the global environmental research:

- the Group on Earth Observation (GEO), the intergovernmental organization working to improve the availability, access and use of Earth observations,
- the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) being built by the GEO to facilitate the sharing of environmental data and information collected from the large array of observing systems contributed by countries and organizations
- the World Meteorological Organization (WMO)
- the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC)
- The Research Data Alliance (RDA)
- the European Space Agency (ESA)
- the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT)
- the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP)
- [Copernicus](#), the European Union's Earth observation programme and some of its Entrusted Entities:
 - the European Environment Agency (EEA)
 - MERCATOR Océan
 - European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF)
 - European Commission DG Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Within D3.4, not all international partners were contacted. It was left as initiative of the single RIs to indicate which international stakeholder were the most relevant to the plurality of RIs. On the other side, WP3 online meetings with international stakeholders were widely communicated within the ENVRI community.

ENVRI as a cluster or as individual RIs took part in conferences and workshops, organised specific events and exchanged information to raise awareness on ENVRI role and most specifically on ENVRI-FAIR developments to those international organisations and agencies. A list of events (non-exhaustive) reported by ENVRI-FAIR project partners can be found in Appendix 1 of this report. Within ENVRI-FAIR WP3, the most important international partners were contacted, to ensure standards and operating principles established by the community are in line with those used in the global networks.

Most specifically, in order to ensure that the definition of minimum quality standards of service in ENVRI-FAIR comply with the international initiatives and that the ENVRI strategy is known, a stakeholders' meeting was organised in April 2021. This virtual event aimed at engaging exchanges between Environmental RIs and international organizations on access to data and data resources and to ensure alignment of policies at all levels. The meeting was attended by 40 participants from ENVRI and their stakeholders. The event helped raising awareness on the ENVRI ecosystem, the specific developments of the ENVRI-Hub. Key stakeholders participating were high-level representatives of the European Space Agency, World Meteorological Organisation, European Centre for Medium-Range Weather forecast on behalf of Copernicus, and Group on Earth Observations. Those stakeholders were found to be the most relevant ones for the ENVRI community as a whole but aren't exhaustive. Minutes of this meeting are summarized in ENVRI-FAIR Milestone 7.³ The strategies exposed during the event are developed below.

3.1 Stakeholder's strategies

The section below illustrates the various approaches to data access strategies and policies followed by large international organizations closely connected to ENVRI. It is worth noting the stakeholders are not directly involved with EOSC but in more targeted Earth observation (EO) relevant platforms.

³ ENVRI-FAIR Milestone MS7: High-level meeting on the alignment of ENVRI-FAIR data policies with International stakeholders - Minutes of meeting

3.1.1 European Space Agency - The ESA Thematic Exploitation Platforms and Data Cube strategy.

The vision of ESA is to enable the maximum benefit of Earth observation for science, society and economic growth in Europe, served by European industry. ESA will implement this vision through its Earth observation programmes⁴. Great transformation in the handling of Earth Observation data has occurred in the last years: before mission ground segments made data available for download and users processed the data on their own infrastructures. Nowadays, with the Copernicus programme and EO satellites generating tremendous data sets, this is no longer possible. These data offer a unique opportunity for science and applications, and to make sure these complex data streams are exploited to their full potential, ESA invested in platform technologies like the Datacube or the Thematic Exploitation Platforms to enable co-creation, co-engineering of products and services.

Three layers of actors are involved in these platforms:

- the data generation layer from satellite and in-situ sources where ENVRI and the ENVRI-Hub are involved;
- the resource tier layer, powered by information and communications technology (ICT) companies; including the Data and Information access services (DIAS). They are a set of cloud-based platforms with central access to data and information.
- the platform service layer (including ESA Thematic Exploitation Platforms (TEPs, openEO and Euro data cube, openEO platform and some ENVRI like EPOS). The TEPs offer a tailored environment for the specific community: the sharing of the data and results are made following the FAIR principles.

In the future, ESA will be involved in several initiatives:

- ESA Digital Twin Earth Programme for R&D supporting the other activities
- Collaboration agreement with DG RTD for Earth System Science activities
- DIAS initiative delegated by DG DEFIS for Copernicus data access on the cloud
- DestinE initiative delegated by DG CNECT in collaboration with ECMWF and EuMetSat

Several cooperation models are foreseen by ESA. The first one is *using space contribution*: ESA provides free-at-point-of-use access to platforms allowing exploitation of space data on the cloud and invests to update space-related platforms/infrastructures as per community needs.

The one found most relevant to ENVRI is the *data access technology* model with platforms (ie Euro Data cube) being used as a tool for shared access. Data collections (as a data cube layers) continue to be owned and managed by the data owner, including decision who gets access at what conditions. Connection via interoperable Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) interfaces preferred to data duplication. Data providers are entitled to a usage fee to cover for data maintenance. Euro Data Cube supports a federated concept and can be installed at the data owner infrastructure. It feeds then the other tools used by environmental community making data available as per latest OGC standards.

The possible models of integration with ENVRI envisaged by ESA and ENVRI are: using space contribution (EPOS model) or data access (ENVRI-Hub) and as infrastructure provider. In the upcoming years, ESA will contribute to *Destination Earth* (see section 3.2 below) rather than EOSC. ENVRI-Hub operation and maintenance could be a subject for Destination Earth.

3.1.2 European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast - ECMWF

The implementation and operation of Copernicus services have been delegated by the European Commission to dedicated service providers - the Copernicus Entrusted Entities - through a series of "Delegation Agreements". ENVRI are involved through procurement contracts with several Entrusted Entities as mentioned in section 2.

ECMWF is one of these Copernicus Entrusted Entities and is responsible for the delivery of the Copernicus Services C3S and CAMS in which several ENVRI (Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS), and In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (IAGOS) are involved).

⁴ [ESA Earth Observation Strategy 2040](#)

The Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Services : Atmosphere data store

ECMWF uses observations to improve the daily forecasts, assess the quality of these forecasts and monitor the exchange of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide at the surface of the Earth.

In the frame of the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), the Atmosphere data store (ADS) was recently developed. ADS approach varies from other data portals as it aims at establishing a unified interactive and programmatic access to most of CAMS datasets. It is replacing the CAMS Products Catalogue as the main point of access to CAMS data. It uses the CDS technology and infrastructure. The ADS is a modular and distributed data and information system which provides access to CAMS datasets through unified web and API interfaces. Constant updates and user-driven improvements are foreseen.

Interoperability is key to the ECMWF be it:

- *at internal level* - between the infrastructure and the distributed data repository where data formats and access protocols must follow internationally recognised open standards and be managed by a recognised international standardisation body (e.g. ISO, WMO, OGC) with datasets and/or services provided having to be documented using the appropriate metadata standards (ISO19115).
- *Or at external:* the most important standards required are recommended by the INSPIRE directive in order to view and download the products and data from the Product catalogue.

Interoperability with wider data access initiatives (WeKEO DIAS, European Weather cloud, EOSC, Destination Earth) is seen as crucial by the ECMWF community. There are many initiatives for **making data available and interoperable**: developing tools to help users **navigate through this landscape would be extremely useful**.

3.1.3 Group on Earth Observations

The Group on Earth Observations (GEO) has more 130 participating organisations including some ENVRI-like ICOS or EPOS. GEO is advocating for informed decisions and actions for the benefit of humankind by coordinated, comprehensive and sustained Earth observations. The construction of the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) is a central part of GEO's mission. **Coordination** is the key aspect with respect to the **In-situ data sharing within GEO landscape**. GEO is composed by a large variety of actors, not only research oriented and resources are based on voluntary contribution.

Data management and data sharing principles in GEOSS are close to FAIR principles but differ slightly. They are briefly outlined below:

- *data, metadata and products will be shared as Open Data by default, by making them available as part of the GEOSS Data Collection of Open Resources for Everyone (Data-CORE) without charge or restrictions on reuse, subject to the conditions of registration and attribution when the data are reused;*
- *where international instruments, national policies or legislation preclude the sharing of data as Open Data, data should be made available with minimal restrictions on use and at no more than the cost of reproduction and distribution; and*
- *all shared data, products and metadata will be made available with minimum time delay.*⁵

The GEO community faces challenges around the definition of in-situ data, technical barriers and a complex international landscape. In-situ data is seen as the bottleneck to have better products in GEO work programme activities. The complexity also arises from the fact that the organisation counts numerous members, each of them having specific data policies. Ensuring the implementation of open data policies requires policy and technical resources. Other principles as **CARE** (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics)⁶ or **TRUST** (Transparency, Responsibility, User

⁵ [GEO Open EO data \(earthobservations.org\)](http://earthobservations.org)

⁶ The International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group (within the Research Data Alliance) is a network of nation-state based Indigenous data sovereignty networks and individuals that developed the 'CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance' (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) in consultation with Indigenous Peoples, scholars, non-profit organizations, and governments extract from Carroll, S.R., Garba, I., et al, 2020. The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p.43. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>

Community, and Sustainability, and Technology)⁷ should be considered additionally to FAIR principles notably when dealing with indigenous knowledge.

Recently, the GEO Programme Board has endorsed new guidance promoting the use of standard open data licenses in order to tackle the legal barriers and uncertainty currently inhibiting open data usage. The [guidance](#) was developed by the [GEO Data Working Group](#) and follows the [GEO Statement on Open Knowledge](#) published in 2021. The newly endorsed data licensing guidance proposes that EO data that can be released openly should be licensed using a standard open data license, widely recognized by data users and containing no substantive restrictions on use⁸.

In terms of in-situ data use, the best way is to look at the individual activities of GEO work programme initiatives, like the GEO land degradation initiative (notably national data sets which can be useful for land degradation). Having this data strategy going towards ESOC and other data spaces is addressing two key bottlenecks: having access to data and being able to reuse what has been produced. It is a good incentive to improve wider sharing of data.

3.2 Other Policies of interest

The ecosystem around Earth observation data from space and in-situ sources keeps on evolving. Several policies are supporting the uptake of environmental data from in-situ and space-based solutions, in support of key EU missions. The examples developed below are seen as key to support further ENVRI developments through specific EU or international initiatives.

Destination Earth (DestinE)

Started in 2021/22, DestinE is a major initiative of the European Commission through DG CONNECT. It aims to develop a very high precision digital model of planet Earth (a ‘digital twin’) to monitor and predict environmental change and human impact to support sustainable development. DestinE supports both the green and digital transitions by pushing the boundaries of Earth-system monitoring and prediction.

EUMETSAT, the ECMWF and ESA are the three entrusted agencies selected by the EC to implement Destination Earth over the next 7 to 10 years. Each entity brings its own expertise and strength to support the initiative. While EUMETSAT is responsible for the *DestinE Data Lake* - creating a coherent and self-standing DestinE data space, ESA is responsible for the DestinE *Core Service Platform* and the ECMWF for the two initial *digital twins* on extreme weather and climate adaptation. Data coming from ENVRI is crucial to this initiative.

To support tackling complex environmental challenges, DestinE aims at helping policy-makers to:

- monitor and simulate the Earth’s system developments (land, marine, atmosphere, biosphere) and human interventions;
- anticipate environmental disasters and resultant socio-economic crises to save lives and avoid large economic downturns;
- enable the development and testing of scenarios for ever more sustainable development.

The DestinE can benefit from Member States investments under their Recovery and Resilience Fund Plans in combination with Digital Europe (in the context of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking), and Horizon Europe for the related research activities.

Through procurement, DestinE can provide an opportunity to further develop the ENVRI-Hub and enhance the update of ENVRI data and services. Under the newly published Work Programme 2023/249, the DestinE initiative will be further implemented putting emphasis on the system activity to reinforce all aspects of the deployed solutions, from data flow to integration and federation of external services as well as to the deployment of an additional range of services, tools and applications. The indicative budget in support to the developments of DestinE for 2023/24 is of 60 M€.

⁷ The TRUST Principles provide a common framework to facilitate discussion and implementation of best practice in digital preservation by all stakeholders. – extract from Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

⁸ [GEO licensing guidance removes barriers to open data sharing \(earthobservations.org\)](#)

⁹ [Digital Europe Programme’s multiannual work programme for 2023 - 2024 | Shaping Europe’s digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

Green Deal Data Space:

The EU data strategy (COM/2020/66) formulates the vision to create a European single market for data where data can flow freely between sectors, countries. Data access and use rely on clear rules. This strategy would have the potential to unlock huge potential of data. The strategy has two aims: first the creation of a cross-sectoral legislative framework (with notably the Data Governance Act, Data Act, Implementing Act on High-value datasets) and secondly the creation of “common EU data spaces¹⁰” (at request of the European Council).

The Green Deal Data Space is an infrastructure that will allow data providers and initiatives to openly share their data to tackle climate change and environmental challenges in a multidisciplinary manner. It will be a federation of data ecosystems enabling policy makers, businesses, researchers, and citizens from EU and around the world to jointly tackle climate change. This data space is supported by the GREAT (Green Deal Space Foundation and its Community of Practice) project funded by the EU's Digital Europe Programme. This project contributes to two European Commission priorities for 2019-2024: the EU Green Deal and the Europe fit for the digital age. The project will deliver a roadmap for implementing and deploying this Green Deal Data Space building on a consortium of 11 partners including ECMWF, some ENVRI and commercial actors.

The new EVE (Earth Virtualization Engine) initiative might also benefit from the engagement of ENVRI into ENVRI-Hub as a coordinated efforts to support a new generation of models.

At international scale, some opportunities could arise from the United Nations ‘Global Digital Compact in support of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This initiative demonstrates UN leadership to tackle climate change and will require important resources including EO data and information to allow governments to identify risks and tailor their policy responses. ENVRI data and services support the reporting of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and indicators.

A Key programme of WMO is the Global Basic Observing Network (GBON; <https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/wigos/gbon>) which strives to ensure sufficient data density to support weather forecasts. The WMO Infrastructure Commission is currently working on a future expansion of GBON in other domains, starting with hydrology and cryosphere, and then climate monitoring, ocean and atmospheric composition. This is why ENVRI must remain fully compatible with WIGOS in the future networks, as well as to answer scientific and societal questions, even those which do not exist today.

A critical aspect to understanding and projecting climate change and to assessing measures to curb emissions is the atmospheric composition. The WMO Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) Programme was established in 1989 in recognition of the need for improved scientific understanding of the increasing influence of human activities on atmospheric composition and subsequent societal impacts. The mission of GAW is to reduce atmospheric composition-related risks to society associated with air pollution, ecosystem and human health, food production, and climate change and support policy and requirements of conventions by providing trusted, high-quality transparent, scientific-based information. Many of the atmospheric research infrastructures (ICOS, ACTRIS, IAGOS) are providing their services to GAW, following the WIGOS standards.

One considerable challenge these measurements efforts pose is their coherent integration to describe the past, and present, and support projection of anticipated future state of the climate system. Bringing this array of measurements into usable and accessible data for more than just specialized user communities, and which improve the description of the state of the Earth system as a whole is a key challenge that must now be addressed. In addition, optimizing all these networks and types of observations so they best complement each other and support and inform actions is another challenge of our near future.

¹⁰ EC Staff Working Document (2022) 45 - Feb 2022 <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6532-2022-INIT/en/pdf>

4 Way forward

Further harmonization

ENVRI community made progress on ensuring standardisation of data with the international stakeholders with ENVRI-FAIR being instrumental to go a step further in FAIR principles. This is well illustrated in the various deliverables of the subdomain fairness, in WP8, WP9, WP10 and WP11. The challenge faced by the ENVRI community is this multicomplex field with a lot of different networks and thus different formats in data and metadata. ENVRI-FAIR helps harmonising variables and formats. The work undertaken in this project on data-sharing and common standards should be further developed within ENVRI. Agreement on best practices is also needed in the assessment of the data. Licenses and access rights are very important. Working as a cluster will help overcoming these bottlenecks and ensure that data is used outside of RI scope.

Further harmonization, common standards, and standardisation of in-situ data are needed as its landscape is very complex. Users would welcome interoperability for accessing in-situ data to facilitate integration to the services (i.e. Copernicus). A task group with stakeholders would be interesting to work on the vocabularies, connecting with the RDA initiative on vocabulary development efforts, to identify gaps and good practices in glossary development, and avoid duplication of effort in an EOSC context.

Setting up sustainable governance within ENVRI

A governance is needed not to lose RI prerogative. RIs should control the way users get access to their data and need to continue to serve key customers and funders. EOSC or platforms like the TEPS or the Copernicus DIAS are a way to create additional services and widen access to what is already provided by RIs but it will not replace what is done at RI level.

Sustainability is also financial and relies on legal frameworks. Implementation of FAIR principles has cost which is often not budgeted by the RIs. The costs of making data FAIR and maintaining this FAIRness (PiDs, storage, DOI, preservation) and the sustainability, traceability and accountability of data providers is still a challenge.

Costs for access to data will affect sustainability model. The federated approach to data integration should rely on a strong implication and harmonization of national financial support.

At the moment, data access relies on EC projects, this does not guaranty the long-term accessibility. The risk of EOSC is to stay locked in the science view without demonstration of the benefits to the citizens which is nonetheless a key to get support in the long term.

The issues related to governance, sustainability, free and open data policy and need for funding to make and keep data FAIR have been expressed in a high-level position paper¹¹ from the ENVRI-FAIR to RIs funders.

Increase ENVRI visibility:

In-situ data comes from myriads of data providers, leading to difficulties for providers to ensure a good visibility in the landscape. Securing data provision in the long-term requires to regularly evaluate whether data services are well responding to user requirements and effectively used. This is performed through data attribution.

Attribution is key to get funded. Within in-situ subgroup of GEO data working group, one of the priorities that had been recognised is to provide a better understanding of the in-situ landscape and demonstrating the benefit of in-situ data to encourage wider use and also the integration of in-situ data with EO data. The importance of communication and user engagement is very important to ensure ENVRI is recognised as a key in-situ data provided by the international stakeholders. This could be done by developing use cases in data working group of GEO.

In-situ data is very important asset and could be used much more via engaging with users notably through platforms like the ESA TEPS, GEOSS platforms or Destination Earth. Open data and simple access are

¹¹ [ENVRI-FAIR EOSC-PositionPaper.pdf](#)

key. There is a strive for wider engagement of ENVRI with other stakeholders and disciplines. The community needs to find a balance between open data and data attribution, understand the implications notably in terms of costs. The demand is to have a maximal use of the RI data. It is important that ENVRI provide data openly and free of charges but need to convince their stakeholders of its usefulness. It is critical that data receive proper attribution and is visible even in the higher-level data products produced by users (ESA, CAMS ...). This is needed to ensure long term sustainable data provision.

It is worth noting that the ENVRI communication efforts will be maintained in the future at the lowest cost by setting up an automated ENVRI website (via RSS feed) and possibly through new INFRA-DEV projects.

4.1.1 Conclusions

Securing the development of the ENVRI-Hub will allow the implementation of the science-based framework for the provision of long-term and high-quality data by the ENVRI, keeping the proper compatibility with the international standards set by ENVRI stakeholders, beyond EOSC. Proper reporting of data in accordance with the FAIR principles, i.e., provenance information as part of rich metadata, and the discoverability of data via enhanced search capabilities through standardised keywords and vocabularies, will also serve and reinforce the international activities of ENVRI.

4.1.2 References

- [ENVRI-FAIR Position Paper on the EOSC](#)
- ENVRI-FAIR [D2.2: ENVRI community building, engagement and communications strategy](#)
- ENVRI-FAIR MS7: High-level meeting on the alignment of ENVRI-FAIR data policies with International stakeholders - Minutes of meeting
- ENVRIPLUS – D17.6 [White paper on further integration of RIs in the environmental field](#)

4.1.3 Appendix A: List of events

Table 1. ENVRI-FAIR presentations towards international stakeholders (based on the data collected for ENVRI-FAIR periodic reports – non-exhaustive list)

Title	Activity type	Conference/meeting/ workshop name	Date	Location
Taking in-situ greenhouse gas information into the big data era	Oral presentation	20th WMO/IAEA Meeting on Carbon Dioxide, Other Greenhouse Gases and Related Measurement Techniques (GGMT2019)	Sept 2019	Jeju, South Korea
Representing ENVRI-FAIR	Panel discussion	EC Workshop on Creating a common European data space for environmental and climate-related data	Sept 2019	Brussels, Belgium
ENVRI-FAIR - Interoperable environmental FAIR data and services for society, innovation and research	Oral presentation	IEEE International Conference on eScience 2019 (eScience2019)	Oct 2019	San Diego, US
EcoPortal	Oral presentation	RDA 14th Plenary – Data Makes the Difference	Oct 2019	Helsinki
ENVRI community – The European Hub to environmental and Earth system in-situ data	Oral presentation and panel discussion	GEOweek 2019	Nov 2019	Canberra Australia
ENVRI-FAIR Overview and Position Paper on the EOSC	Oral presentation	ESFRI Task Force meeting on EOSC	Jan 2020	Brussels, Belgium
ENVRI-FAIR and FAIRness assessment methodologies	Presentation	Digital Earth Annual Meeting 2020	May 2020	Virtual
ENVRI cluster for Digital Twin Earth	Oral presentation	PHI WEEK 2020	Oct 2020	Virtual
The ENVRI-Hub – Approach, design and architecture	Oral presentation and discussion	RDA2021	April 2021	Virtual

Title	Activity type	Conference/meeting/ workshop name	Date	Location
FAIR Alignment of ENVRI with International stakeholders	Oral presentation	ENVRI meets stakeholders: High-level meeting on the alignment of ENVRI-FAIR data policies with international stakeholders	April 2021	Virtual
The researchers' viewpoint on EOSC	Presentation	Open Science Spring days	May 2021	Virtual
ENVRI Cluster	Oral presentation and discussion	ESFRI Science Clusters Workshop	June 2021	Virtual
Interconnecting and integrating ERICs across disciplines and challenges	Panel	ERIC Stakeholders' Workshop on European Research Infrastructures Consortia	Sept 2021	Virtual
Increasing FAIRness of marine data within ENVRI-FAIR	Oral presentation	International Ocean Data Conference	Feb 2022	Poland
		International Data Week	June 2022	Virtual
FAIR environmental data for EOSC and the World: Engineering the ENVRI-Hub	Panel	RDA 20th Plenary Co-located Event	Mar 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden
ENVRI	Oral and panel discussion	RDA Plenary	Mar 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden
Open and FAIR environmental data for societal benefits, an ENVRI-FAIR policy event	Event	ENVRI-FAIR policy event	June 2023	Lund, Sweden